

Characterisation and Assessment of Defects in CFRP Laminates

Graham Clark

Aircraft Materials Division,
DSTO Aeronautical Research Laboratory
Melbourne, Australia

Abstract

Fibre-composite materials are being used increasingly in critical aerospace applications. These materials are prone to in-service damage by low-energy impact; this requires assessment and possibly repair, leading to a requirement for NDI techniques capable of ensuring that such damage is detected and characterized correctly. This paper describes an ultrasonic time-of-flight C-scanning system developed at ARL, which can provide detailed information about the structure of internal damage in carbon fibre reinforced laminates and which permits accurate sizing of sub-surface defects. Also described is a model developed by the author which correctly predicts the morphology of impact damage in a range of laminates.

Characterisation of Damage in Composites by NDI

Defects in composite laminates includes porosity, inclusions, delaminations or resin-rich areas, all of which may be introduced during manufacture while delaminations and fibre fracture may be introduced in service by impact or abnormal loading. The majority of these defects can be detected at manufacture using non-destructive inspection methods based on ultrasonic amplitude C-scanning; the presence of damage, porosity or inclusions or other attenuating defect is indicated by a reduction in the amplitude of the back-face or transmitted signal. This method, however, indicates only that there is a change in signal attenuation in any particular area; it is unable to reveal the detailed structure of any defect which is found, and does not permit detailed assessment of the significance of that damage. In-service inspection of aircraft components is usually limited to time-consuming hand-scanning of suspect areas to detect and size service-induced impact damage which can degrade laminate compression strength; this approach is far from ideal when it comes to inspecting areas which are regarded as "possibly damaged", or for determining accurately the size and through-thickness distribution of damage prior to repair.

There is clearly a need for an NDI technique which can scan a limited area of a composite component and determine accurately the size and distribution of any damage present. ARL has developed an ultrasonic C-scanning system (Fig.1) which will satisfy both of these requirements [1]. The technique used is similar to conventional (amplitude) ultrasonic C-scanning in that an ultrasonic probe is traversed over the specimen. However, the ARL system uses signal time-of-flight measurements, with appropriate gating, to provide detailed information about the depth location of any damage present. The system is portable, and is capable of being mounted on the aerodynamic surfaces of an aircraft in any orientation (Fig. 1). The ultrasonic signal is introduced using a pseudo-dry coupling technique which avoids the need for conventional couplant or water-jet systems. The head is scanned over the area of interest under computer control, and defects at different depths in the laminate are displayed in real time using colour-coding of the image, permitting easy visualisation of the damage distribution and individual damage features. The system has been tested by sectioning of impact-damaged laminates, and has been shown to provide assessment of damage size to within 1mm, and to give depth location to within approximately ± 1 ply. The unit has been demonstrated satisfactorily on an aircraft.

Figure 1(b) shows an example of the use of the ARL time-of-flight C-scanning system to assess the nature and extent of impact damage in aircraft

components. This particular example is part of a wing skin panel from a high-performance fighter aircraft which was damaged in a mid-air collision. In addition to revealing the extent of the damage, the C-scan clearly reveals the depth location of delaminations, and provides considerable potential as a means of assessing potential repair procedures.

Modelling of Impact Damage in Composites

In parallel with the development of practical NDI procedures for composites, ARL has also been involved in developing a capability for improved evaluation of damaged laminates. Part of this work involves modelling the structure of typical impact damage in various laminates. Worldwide, considerable effort has been devoted to the numerical modelling of delamination behaviour in composites; the numerical techniques have concentrated almost exclusively on the simplest configuration - a single delamination - with varying degrees of success. However, the effect of real impact damage on mechanical properties is more severe than that of a single delamination, and the modelling of real impact damage effects is considerably more difficult, in view of the complexity of the impact damage structure. One problem is determining which form of impact damage will have the most severe consequences, and in this regard, an understanding of the morphology of the delamination and cracking involved in impact damage could be of considerable value.

A model developed at ARL [2] has been shown to provide predictions consistent with the observed delamination structure in laboratory-damaged CRFP laminates in various configurations. The model explains why delaminations occur preferentially at certain interfaces and provides a means of predicting the relative size of delaminations and the occurrence of prominent delamination/cracking features.

The model was developed from observations of the symmetry seen in sections of impact-damaged CFRP material [2] and is shown in Fig. 2. Consider two adjacent, non-parallel plies (shown for convenience as $+45^\circ$ and -45°) under impact. The plies are clamped remotely, and impacted with a blunt indenter (or by forces transmitted through intervening plies), producing damage under the indenter and in the annular zone between the indenter and the remote support. Figure 2(a) illustrates schematically the deflection of the pair of plies; the forces operating on the plies in two regions, labelled A and B, between the indenter and the remote support are indicated. At A, the deflections induce fibre tension in both plies, resulting in peel forces acting to promote delamination. Conversely, at B, the ply curvatures and tensions produce a net force acting to keep the plies together, and delamination would not be favoured. Hence, the model suggests that delamination is most favoured in the region away from the impact centreline in the direction of the lower ply.

The model was tested on a variety of layups and impact conditions; Fig.2(b) shows results for a 10-ply face laminate forming part of a honeycomb-core structural sheet. Sequential sectioning of the laminate revealed the delamination structure shown. Also shown is the delamination structure predicted by the model. Agreement is excellent; at every delaminated interface, the preferred orientation of the delamination is that of the lower ply, whether this be 0° , 90° , $+45^\circ$ or -45° . The sizes of the "predicted" and observed delaminations are also consistent with the model [2].

The model has also been tested against other laminate layups and impact conditions, with a high level of success; further development of the model is shown in Fig. 3, to include the effects of ply cracking. In the upper ply, the various local stress components are such as to produce intra-ply resin cracking as illustrated. The interface between the upper ply (in Fig.3a) and the next ply above it in the laminate is subjected to high peel stresses in the vicinity of the ply cracks, and a "top-hat" arrangement of

delaminations and cracking such as that shown in Fig. 3b would be expected to be a feature in the impact damage zone. The upper-level delamination in such a "top-hat" arrangement would be partly bounded by the resin cracks and would occur near to the impact centreline, while the lower-level delaminations are the major impact damage delaminations which occur in the regions predicted by the model. Such a "top-hat" structure is observed in many impact damage cases, and is believed to be a major sub-unit of the impact damage structure. It is also possible to envisage a three-dimensional stacking of these sub-units in a low-energy configuration; this structure can in some laminates represent many of the features observed in real impact damage situations.

The ability of the basic model to predict preferred delamination orientation, the prominence of the "top-hat" delamination/cracking feature in sections of damaged laminates, and the way in which these features may be linked in stacks, suggests that the apparent complexity of composite impact damage may be explained to a large extent by fairly simple delamination and cracking mechanisms.

References

- [1] Preuss, T.E. and Clark, G. "Use of time-of-flight C-scanning for assessment of impact damage in composites", Composites 19 (2) (1988) pp 145-148.
- [2] Clark, G. "Modelling of Impact Damage in Composites" Composites, May 1989.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: (a) ARL portable C-scanning system for NDI of composites, in use on an F/A-18 aircraft, (b) C-scan obtained using the laboratory version of the ARL ultrasonic system; damage at various depths within a wing panel is shown in various colours.

Figure 2: (a) Basic impact damage model, (b) Predicted and observed delamination damage in a 10-ply composite coupon.

Fig.3 More detailed representation of the damage, showing (a) cracking and (b) formation of a "top-hat" cracking and delamination structure.